

VIEWERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS MALAYALAM NEWS CHANNELS IN KERALA

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Abstract

In Kerala there was TV broadcasting from the early days by the Doordarsan. But the private channels entered the market in the 1990s. Only after that, the competition in market started and it brought the quality picture as to withstand in the stiff competitive conditions. Keralities are reaching all parts of the world in search of their living. This widens the geographical scope of satellite channels even to Europe, America, Middle East and Singapore. There are about six Malayalam news channels at present. Each one of them is competing to capture the attention of viewers. As per the study most preferred malayalam news channel was asianet and people prefer to watch detailed news and live news. They also spend very less time for watching news channels.

Keywords: types of news, age group. Time spend, exaggeration of news

Introduction

The television channel industry has grown tremendously today. It is the only industry which does not have any hartals or lock outs in Kerala. As compared to earlier period number news channels has increased and there exist a tight competition between the news channels. Majority of television viewers across Kerala looks for news and news based programmes such as live news, talk shows, debates etc. The media covers news of public interest such as political happenings, sports, city news, national news, international news, business, education, entertainment, literature and medical news. The news should satisfy all men, women and children of various age-group and status. At present there are six Malayalam news channels. They are Asianet news, Manorama news, Mathrubhumi news, Reporter, People TV and Media one.

Research Problem

The news industry in Kerala is growing at a very high speed and competition between the news channels are also increasing day by day. The success of news channels depends upon the perception of viewers. In order to capture the attention of viewers each channels are presenting the news in different ways. Each one of us is able to know about each and every event that is occurring in our country, this is only because of the efforts undertaken by the news channels. Lot of employees are working behind the news channel to collect the news, edit them and to present it in an attractive way. Now a day, it's seen that news channels are trying to exaggerate their news. How far this exaggeration of news will help to capture the attention of viewers? Which news channel is mostly preferred by viewers? Which types of news are preferred by viewers? Do the news readers or reporters influence the viewers? To find answers to these questions there is a need to conduct a study in this aspect.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the viewers perception about Malayalam news channel in Kerala.
- To identify the time spend by the viewers varies according to their age group or not.
- To know viewers perception about motives of each channel.

Hypotheses

- H0: There is no significant difference between time spend by the viewers with regard to their age group.
- H0: There is no significant difference in the opinion of viewers about the motives of each channel

Research Methodology and Data Base

The study was designed as a descriptive one based on both primary data and secondary data.

Secondary Data

The secondary data, necessary for the study was collected from various sources:

- Journals
- Magazines
- Website.

Sample Design

All Malayalam news channels were taken for the study. 60 samples were drawn from the viewers of Malayalam news channels using convenient sampling method. From among the 14 districts in Kerala only 2 districts were chosen for the study. From the Southern part of Kerala, Cochin was selected and from the Northern part, Kozhikode district was selected.

Tools used for Data Collection

A well structured questionnaire was developed to collect information from the viewers of Malayalam news channels.

Tools for Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis various statistical tools and mathematical techniques were used such as:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi square test

List of Variables used for the Study

- Age group
- News channels
- Types of news
- Efforts of news readers or reporters
- Exaggeration of news

Limitations of the Study

As in the case of almost all social science research, this study is also not free from certain inherent limitations as stated below:

1. Most of the primary data collected from respondents are based on their memories, and may be subject to memory errors.
2. Being a social study, the study is not free from the defects of social investigation.

Results and Discussions

The results of the analysis of primary data collected are presented below.

Table no.1 shows the most preferred Malayalam news channel

Malayalam news channel	No. of respondents	Per cent
Asianet news	32	33
Manorama news	28	29
Mathrubhumi news	16	17
Reporter	12	13
People TV	0	0
Media one	8	8
Total	96	100

Data Source: Primary data

As per the analysis, majority of the viewers (33%) opined that Asianet News channel is the most preferred Malayalam news channel and 29% opined that it is Manorama news.

Table no.2 shows the time spend by viewers for watching news channels

Time spend by viewers	No. of respondents	Per cent
Less than 1 hour	32	53
1-2 hour	16	27
2-5 hour	8	13
More than 5 hour	4	7
Total	60	100

Data Source: Primary data

Majority of the viewers (53%) opined that they spend only less than one hour daily for watching news channels and only 7% opined that they watches news channels for more than five hours.

Table no.3 shows time spends by different age groups for watching news channels.

Time spend\Age	Below 18	18-30	31-50	51-70	Above 70	Total
Less than 1 hour	3	17	9	2	1	32
1 hour -2 hour	0	3	8	4	1	16
2 hour - 5 hour	0	0	2	4	2	8
More than 5hour	0	0	0	2	2	4
Total	3	20	17	5	5	50

Chi square value:33.17, df:12, P value: 0.0009

Data Source: Primary data

In order to test whether the time spend by the viewers for watching news channels varies according to the age group, the following hypothesis was formulated and it was tested using Chi square test.

H0: There is no significant difference between time spend by the viewers with regard to their age group.

As the P-value obtained (0.0009) at the degrees of freedom 12 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis formulated will be rejected. So it can be concluded that the time spend by the viewers for watching news channels varies according to their age group.

Table no.4 shows viewers opinion about types of news preferred

News preferred	No.	Per cent
Head line news	16	15
Detailed news	40	39
Live news	28	27
Debates	16	15
News scrolling	4	4
Total	104	100

Data Source: Primary data

As per the above table, about 39% of the viewers prefer detailed news, 27 % prefer live news, and 15% prefer headline news and debates.

Table no.5 shows viewers opinion about news readers or reporters influence in choosing channel

News readers or reporters influence in choosing channel	No. of respondents	Per cent
Yes	8	13
No	52	87
Total	60	100

Data Source: Primary data

Most of the viewers (87%) opined that news readers or reporters does not influence them in choosing channel

Table no.6 shows viewers opinion about news channel exaggerates the news or not

Exaggerate the news	No. of respondents	Per cent
Yes	44	73
No	16	27
Total	60	100

Data Source: Primary data

Most of the viewers opined that all news channels exaggerate their news.

Table – 7: shows motives of channels

Motive	Asianet news		Manorama news		Mathrubhumi news		Reporter		People TV		Media one	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Increase rating	42	70	39	65	48	80	51	85	32	53	37	62
Safeguard specific group	11	18	7	12	3	5	5	8	4	7	15	25
Social benefit	7	12	14	23	9	15	4	7	24	40	8	13
TOTAL	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100	60	100
Chi square value:43.62, df:10, P value: 0.000000385												

Data source: Primary data

As per the above table, more than 50 % of the viewers opined that main motive of each channel is to increase their ratings. In order to identify whether viewers opinion varies according to the news channels, the following hypothesis was formulated.

H0: There is no significant difference in the opinion of viewers about the motives of each channel

As the P-value obtained (0.000000385) at the degrees of freedom 10 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis formulated will be rejected. So it can be concluded that the viewers' opinion about the motives of the channels varies according to the channels.

Findings

- Asianet news and Manorama news is the most preferred news channel and the viewers are interested to watch detailed news and live news.
- Age group of the viewers is one of the important factor that influence the time spend for watching news channels. The study reveals that according to the changes in the age group time spend by them also varies.
- News readers or the reporter does not influence the viewers in choosing channels.
- Almost all the channels exaggerate their news.
- Main motive of the channels are to increase their rating. But when a detailed evaluation is done, it was found that motive varies according to the channels.

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